

Optical plastics – a wonder material^ψ

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It is the materials which actually enable us to realize our concepts or hypotheses into reality. In the prehistoric periods, metallic materials were required for survival and building materials were necessary for the construction of houses for the humans. A new development took place every time which was always associated with the creation of a different type of material. Several technological advances have been made possible by our ever increasing understanding of the basic structure of materials. If we look back and analyze each of the technological breakthroughs, we would realize that all this could become possible only due to our scientific understanding of materials.

One of the most studied natural phenomena by mankind pertains to light or optics. Ever since man came into existence on earth, his curiosity about stars and other planets surrounding him was always the subject of interest. In order to understand various objects, it was necessary to have devices which could utilize the science of optics. For devices, there existed the need for materials with surfaces to reflect, refract, transmit and disperse the light.

Technologies based on electronic, optical and magnetic phenomena are the key to the convergence of computing, communication and consumer electronics. These technological capabilities which have enabled the information age, are fundamentally changing how we live, interact and transact business. Optics, a branch of science dealing with the study of the behavior of light rays has seen tremendous developments since the discovery of the first optical material, glass. Glass was a serendipitous discovery in 5000 B.C. Later, glass was responsible for the invention of spectacles in the 13th century by Roger Bacon and then for telescopes in the 16th century by Galileo Galilei.

As our understanding of materials increased, replacement of glass by alternate materials, such as plastics and

polymers took place. The use of plastics in optical devices started in the 19th century with the discovery of poly methyl methacrylate and polycarbonate. These materials made possible, the invention of sophisticated optical devices such as contact lenses and intraocular lenses in the field of health care. Polymers have become the most promising candidates in the present scenario of high speed telecommunication, optical signal processing, optical computing and networking. It will not be an exaggeration if we term optical plastics as a wonder material!

Optical devices

Light travels at a speed of 3×10^8 m/s. Light has the ability to travel in straight lines and in waves. Devices which can control the speed, amplitude and direction of light passing through them are called optical devices. The ability of light rays to bend, reflect and refract when the light passes through is determined by different optical properties of the material used in the device.

The essential properties that determine the performance of the optical devices can be classified as described below :

(1) Refractive index : The ratio of the velocity of light in vacuum to the velocity of light in any medium is called the refractive index of the material. The composition and structure of the material would affect the velocity of light passing through the material and hence the refractive index of a material becomes significant while selecting the material.

$$n = c/v$$

c = velocity of light in vacuum

v = velocity of light in medium

(2) Transmission : Depending upon the ability of the material to absorb the passing light, the materials are termed as transparent, translucent and opaque. Materials having the ability to let the light pass through completely

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

Table 1. Types of optical devices

Optical device	Parameters	Materials used
A. Lenses :		
(a) Spectacles	Refractive index, optical clarity, Abbe number	Glass, Polythiourethanes, Polyacrylates, Polycarbonates
(b) Sun glasses	Refractive index, UV-resistance, aesthetics	Glass, Polyacrylates
(c) Contact lenses	Refractive index, clarity, biocompatibility, softness/rigidity	Polacrylates and modified acrylates, Silicones and modified silicones
(d) Intraocular lenses	Refractive index, transparency, biocompatibility, softness/rigidity	Polacrylates and modified acrylates, Silicones and modified silicones
(e) Binoculars	Magnifying power, refractive index, clarity	Glass, Polyacrylates, Polycarbonates
(f) Telescopes	Magnifying power, refractive index, clarity	Glass, Polyacrylates, Polycarbonates
(g) Magnifying glass	Magnifying power, refractive index, clarity	Glass, Polyacrylates, Polycarbonates
B. Optical waveguides	Refractive index, absorbance/transmittance	Lithium niobate (LiNbO ₃), Potassium titanyl phosphate (KTiOPO ₄)
C. Optical fibres	Refractive index, rate of light transmission	Glass, Polyacrylates
D. Optical modulators	Refractive index, total internal reflection, infrared absorbance	Lithium niobate (LiNbO ₃), Potassium titanyl phosphate (KTiOPO ₄)
E. Optical demodulators	Refractive index, total internal reflection, infrared absorbance	Lithium niobate (LiNbO ₃), Potassium titanyl phosphate (KTiOPO ₄)
F. Optical interconnectors	Refractive index, total internal reflection, infrared absorbance	Lithium niobate (LiNbO ₃), Potassium titanyl phosphate (KTiOPO ₄)
G. Liquid crystal displays (LCD)	Refractive index, absorbance/transmittance	Glass, Polyacrylates

are termed transparent materials, whereas those which absorb a part of the light and let the remaining light to pass through are termed translucent; materials which absorb all the light rays without letting any light pass through and are termed as opaque.

Opaque materials will therefore have zero transmittance, translucent materials will have a transmittance of < 100% while transparent materials are expected to show 100% transmittance.

Depending upon the application, optical devices are accordingly designed. A brief summary of what is expected of a given optical device and the presently used material for that purpose is given in Table 1.

Classification of optical materials

Gradient index materials :

Materials with different refractive indices are used in applications such as CD players, laser diode collimators,

camera lenses, camcorders, night vision appliances, optical storage devices, fiber optics etc.

Based on refractive index, materials are classified into three commonly known categories :

- (a) Low refractive index (1.30–1.50)
- (b) Medium refractive index (1.50–1.60)
- (c) High refractive index (1.60–1.70)

The materials with higher refractive index would be light weight and therefore they would be the preferred material of choice.

Infrared refractive materials :

Infrared refractive materials are used for image detection in mid and low wavelength infrared applications ($800\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Such applications are important for defense, industrial robotics, medical diagnosis, environmental and chemical process monitoring, forensic drug analysis, microscopy, astronomy, and fourier transform IR spectroscopy.

Fused silica, crown, flint, borosilicate glass and plastics such as polycarbonate are used for the production of IR optical components.

Ultraviolet refractive materials

Refractive material for UV optical regions ($200\text{--}800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are used in optical systems for photo mask printing, photo resist circuit boards, forensic photography etc.

Fused silica, crown, flint and borosilicate glass and plastics such as polycarbonate are used for the production of UV visible optical components.

Materials for optical devices

As can be seen from Table 1, the most common materials for optical applications are glass and plastics.

(a) *Optical glass :*

Upto the 18th century, homogeneity of glass components was a major drawback. For improvements in homogeneity, modification in the process of glass making was desired. A Swiss watch maker, Pierre Guinand was the person associated with the invention of optical glass in the 18th century. He discovered a process for stirring the glass whilst it was molten and so removed the bubbles and unevenness in the mixture. This method was highly successful and resulted in the material known as optical glass.

Glass by itself is a very clear material having a refractive index of 1.45. The refractive index of optical glass can be improved from 1.450–2.022 by the addition of

oxides such as boron oxide, zinc oxide, lanthanum oxide, zirconium oxide and niobium oxide. The Abbe number of optical glass varies from 20 to 85. Fluorescence, solarisation and scintillation are additional properties which gain importance in optical glasses for special applications.

The fragility of glass was a major disadvantage and needed improvement. For this, additives such as lead oxide and boron oxide were used to impart hardness to the glass. This made the availability of three types of glasses to the industry. Among optical glasses, three varieties which are popularly used are :

Crown glass :

Crown glass is a soda-lime-silica composition containing silicon dioxide, sodium oxide and calcium oxide.

Flint glass :

Flint glasses are high density, high dispersion, high refractive index glasses with 45–65% of lead oxide. The currently known flint glasses have a refractive index between 1.45–2.00.

Borosilicate glass :

Glasses containing boron oxide instead of lead oxide are called borosilicate glass. They have high refractive index and low dispersion and high thermal stability.

Advantages of optical glass :

- (1) High scratch resistance
- (2) High transparency

Disadvantages of optical glass :

- (1) Very poor impact resistance
- (2) Dense material

It is the disadvantages associated with glass that forced for the development of alternate materials, such as polymeric materials with optical properties.

(b) *Polymeric materials :*

Polymers are basically compounds having a large number of monomer units as repeating units. Due to their several virtues, polymers have been the preferred material than glass. The advantages associated with the polymeric materials are as follows :

(1) Polymers have very significant design flexibilities and capabilities, especially in the semiconductor industry where devices made from inorganic materials are rapidly approaching the limits of their capabilities.

(2) Polymers can be integrated with electronic devices, such as integrated circuits, in process compatible steps.

(3) Polymers can be cost effective; an important issue in the development of any device.

There are several polymeric materials which also meet the basic requirements for their use in optical devices. Such polymeric materials are also termed as optical plastics.

Optical plastics

Polymeric materials whose backbone (monomer) chain is composed of C, H, O, N and S, possess qualities of glass and hence, are preferred optical materials. When choosing a polymer material for optical applications, optical properties such as clarity, transmittance, birefringence, yellowness index, haze, and refractive index need to be considered.

Other properties to be considered are abrasion resistance, chemical strength, impact resistance, tensile strength, modulus and dimensional stability. The refractive index of a polymer is related to its composition and chemical structure and it depends on the polarizability of the macromolecules i.e. measurement of the electron cloud of the atoms forming the macromolecules.

The two basic types of optical plastics are thermoplastic and thermoset.

Thermosets consist of chemistries in which the reaction takes place during the creation of the parts or in other words during setting of the material in a mould. Thermosets are crosslinked where linear chains are joined irreversibly during molding into an interconnected molecular network and such materials cannot be remolded. Such crosslinkings can be initiated by heat, chemical agents, radiation or a combination of these. Some examples of thermoset polymers are polythiourethane, modified polyacrylates and modified silicates.

Unlike the thermosets, the thermoplastic resin can be softened repeatedly without undergoing a change in chemical composition. Thermoplastics are linear polymer chain where the chains remain linear and separate after molding. Remolding can be thus achieved repeatedly without adversely affecting the quality. Some common examples of thermoset materials are polyacrylates and polystyrene.

The principal optical polymers are :

(1) Acrylics are readily moldable having good stability, and easy to machine and polish. The transmission of acrylics is 92% making its optical clarity most suitable for optical applications.

(2) Polystyrene is used for lenses requiring thin cross sections. Polystyrene has a transmission of 88%.

(3) Thiourethanes are the class of polymers which can be used to produce high refractive index polymers. High refractive index polymers are used for the manufacture of aesthetically pleasing and light lenses.

(4) Polycarbonate is a very tough polymer that gives good performance over a wide temperature range (-140 to 120°C). Its high impact strength makes it especially suitable for streetlight lenses, construction lights and road-work warning lights.

(5) Methyl pentene is a tough, lightweight plastic having superb electrical properties. It is unaffected by many chemicals at temperatures upto 160°C.

(6) CR39 : Allyl diglycol carbonate is commonly known as CR-39. It is used to fabricate eyeglass lenses. It has excellent clarity, abrasion resistance, impact resistance and chemical resistance.

(7) Copolymer of epoxies, silicones, acrylics and urethanes are other thermoset materials used for various optical applications.

Applications of optical plastics

Optical plastics are rapidly replacing the conventional material, glass in spectacle lenses. Design flexibility, light weightedness and impact resistance are the major advantages of plastic lenses making it more comfortable and aesthetic to the wearer.

There are special group of optical plastics which are physiologically inert and have the ability to absorb water. The hydrophilicity of these polymers is due to the presence of water solubilizing groups such as -OH, -COOH and -CONH₂ etc. Such polymeric material are promising candidates for biomedical devices such as contact lenses. The major criteria for contact lenses is that the corneal surface must be kept wet and oxygenated to remain transparent and healthy which can be met by the presence of hydrophilic groups. By suitable modification of hydrophilic end groups, even hydrophobicity can be introduced thus making it suitable for applications such as intraocular lenses. The polymer scientists have continuously worked on the improvement of optical plastics by virtue of which, today, a number of biomedical optical devices are available in the market such as soft, toric, gas permeable and tinted contact lenses. Phacoemulsification, a popular surgery technique for cataract surgery has been made possible only due to the development of foldable intraocular plastic lenses.

Apart from spectacle and contact lenses optical plastics find application in telescopes, binoculars, microscopes, cameras, wind shields and many more.

These properties have contributed to the extended use of plastic optics. The greatest motivation has been the development of fabrication and replication techniques, creating opportunities for the production of unique optical components and systems not achievable with glass.

Processing of optical plastics

Plastic optics such as eyewear use thermoset polymers, where, they are processed by casting. During casting, a liquid monomer stored at low temperature is introduced into mold where it is polymerized into a part taking the shape of the mold.

Plastic optics other than eyewear such as windshields, camera lenses and telescopic lenses is routinely fabricated from previously polymerized materials using small pellets as starting materials. The pellets are heated to molten state then molded to the desired shape.

Two molding techniques, compression and injection molding are used in high volume production to achieve the desired shape. In compression molding, the melt is compressed and heated in a vertical flatbed press while undergoing a heating cycle. The process is capable of achieving details less than a micron where detail rather than quality is important.

For high quality plastic optics, injection molding is used. The liquid melt is injected into a temperature controlled mold under pressure where it solidifies. The tooling mold design is highly specialized and is the most expensive part of the injection molding process.

The injection molding process has the advantages of including many components and features into a single part. The very fine surface finish quality, has made possible the creation of plastic components for a wide variety of applications. Examples are medical disposables, consumer products, military products and intraocular lenses. Injection molding process is advantageous where optical, mechanical and electrical functions are combined in a single part.

Advantages of optical plastics :

- (1) Low density.
- (2) Low material cost.
- (3) Impact resistant.
- (4) Thermal stability.
- (5) High transmittance of incident light.
- (6) Safety involved in their use because when optical polymers break, the fragments tend to be large and obtuse and hence pose less danger.

Disadvantages of optical plastics :

- (1) Low abrasion resistance – scratch resistant coat-

ings are available for some optical polymers, such as poly methyl methacrylate and polycarbonate. Coatings are necessary for a few applications such as ophthalmic lenses.

- (2) Poor tolerance of large temperature fluctuations.

Design criteria for optical plastics :

- (1) Evaluation of the environment in which the plastic is to be used.
- (2) Physical and optical properties of the plastics.
- (3) Physical properties to be considered are density, hardness, rigidity.
- (4) Service temperature, thermal expansion, electrical and thermal conductivity.

Polymers with existing optical properties can be suitably modified to achieve better optical properties such as higher refractive index, better hardness and better clarity. For example, metal atoms can be incorporated into the polymers to improve refractive index, hardness and transparency. Incorporation of nano-sized metal atoms is very effective to improve the optical properties.

Future of optical plastics

With the advancements made in the field of telecommunication, speed is the keyword for the modern telecommunication industry. Nanosecond is the maximum speed at which information can be transmitted.

Optical polymers have the ability to turn light on and off over a hundred billion times per second, steer an antenna beam with no moving parts in a few millionths of a second from one cell phone caller to another or hold hundreds of tiny beads of genetic material on a small slide in very precise arrays for bioanalytical machine testing.

Optical plastics have a key role to play in the following areas :

(a) *Communications :*

In the fields of high speed telecommunication, optical signal processing, optical computing and networking, planar integrated optical devices are the key functional devices to carry and manipulate signals.

Electro optic modulators : are used to convert digital electronic signals into pulses of light for transmission over fiber optics.

Devices made up of optical plastics can be combined for efficient transmission of data over the internet backbone or to major data processing facilities.

Optical interconnects : Optical plastics can effectively

replace copper connections currently used between processors and memory devices. Slow speed copper connections are becoming serious bottlenecks to achieving higher systems performance.

Optical plastics have the potential to solve this problem by enabling very high speed optical connections.

Organic light emitting diodes (OLED) : Optical plastics can be used to develop photoluminescent and electroluminescent materials coatings for optical devices.

Photomasks : Optical polymers can be used to develop coating material for integrated circuit boards which can be immediately removed from the circuit after use and reused.

(b) *Medicine* :

Optical plastics can be used to develop miniature devices such as catheters, stents and miniaturized surgical tools.

Conclusions :

In the beginning of the chapter, we had referred to optical plastics as a wonder material. Having described various aspects of optical devices, the issues related to

the use of optical devices, the materials generally used for this purpose and the promise that optical plastics present vis-a-vis the conventionally used glass it must have become understandable as to why we call it a wonder material.

In future, the sophisticated devices meeting stringent requirements as far as the optical properties are considered would be in demand. Optical plastics are the only material with the possibility of manoevrability to obtain the desired characteristics.

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